

This is the macro splendidness model, and it goes as followed:

- This is the explainer date mirror twin paradox, and it is made of the following components: The mental paired with the physical, the extra of the objective reality, and the outcome of the spiritual, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired mental with the physical, then objective reality, however, if objective reality, then spiritual, however, if spiritual, then paired mental with the physical. This twin paradox explained and shown before produces a conversion switch called the founders founder reference conversion projection switch, where the reference conversion twin paradox is made of the following components: The brain paired with the material, the extra of the existence, and the outcome of the acceptance, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired brain with the material, then existence, however, if existence, then acceptance, however, if acceptance, then paired brain with the material. This twin paradox explained and shown before proceeds to get switched by the projection switch twin paradox, which is made of the following components: The quantity paired with the quality, the extra of the appear, and the outcome of the script, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired quantity with the quality, then appear, however, if appear, then script, however, if script, then paired quantity with the quality. This twin paradox explained and shown before produces the name for the explainer date mirror twin paradox, which is called the happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox. Then, there are 4 twin paradoxes that are produced by the naming of the twin paradox, where the 1st twin paradox is made of the following components: The mental paired with the brain, the extra of the quantity, and the outcome of the happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired mental with the brain, then quantity, however, if quantity, then happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, however, if happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, then paired mental with the brain. The 2nd twin paradox is made of the following components: The physical paired with the material, the extra of the quality, and the outcome of the happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired physical with the material, then quality, however, if

quality, then happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, however, if happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, then paired physical with the material. The 3rd twin paradox is made of the following components: The objective reality paired with the existence, the extra of the appear, and the outcome of the happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired objective reality with the existence, then appear, however, if appear, then happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, however, if happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, then paired objective reality with the existence. The 4th twin paradox is made of the following components: The spiritual paired with the acceptance, the extra of the script, and the outcome of the happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired spiritual with the acceptance, then script, however, if script, then happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, however, if happen magically absolutely finally perpetually Angrboda splendidness macro splendidness Angrboda perpetually finally absolutely magically happen date mirror twin paradox, then paired spiritual with the acceptance.

This model explained and shown above is the macro splendidness model, and I use this model in my brain, where no other people use this model.

Proceed to install this model in to the verse and my brain, and where this install set is timed as 10:41, and is dated as the 23rd day of the 2nd month, of the 1st year, of the 1st decade.